

maintained there throughout the experiment. Urea and ammonium sulfate were applied singly or in 3 equal splits at 4, 25, and 45 d after transplanting (DT). Sulfur-coated urea (SCU) at 38.6% N, coal tar extract (4 ml/100 g urea)-treated urea (CEU), neem cake (20% wt/wt of urea)-blended urea (NCU), and N-serve

(1% of N in acetone)-treated urea were the other treatments (see table). One pot each was used at 25 and 45 d to record dry matter (DM) accumulation and N uptake.

Urea and ammonium sulfate had similar yields at all stages. Slow-release and nitrification-inhibitor-treated fertilizers

had little effect except for the slight response to CEU and NCU at the second stage and NCU at maturity. N release from SCU did not meet the plant N requirements. Lack of response to nitrification inhibitors could be due to heat-labile components in the coal tar extract and N-serve, which decompose in tropical temperatures. □

Response of rice to phosphorus fertilizer in different crop rotations

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Most fertilizer recommendations are based on fertilizer response data for a single crop. For efficient use of a limited input like P, however, residual effects should be considered when formulating fertilizer use recommendations for different cropping sequences.

In 1979-83 we evaluated fertilizer P requirements for field rotations of wheat - rice, wheat - maize (fodder) - rice, and berseem - rice. The rabi crops of wheat and berseem *Trifolium alexandrinum* L. received the recommended dose of 120, 13,

25 and 25, 32.7, 0 kg NPK/ha. The following rice crop was grown with 0, 13, or 26 kg P/ha to determine the crop's relative response to residual P. Soil was a nonsaline loamy sand with pH 8.2, 0.17% organic carbon, and low available P. PR106 rice was transplanted the 4th wk of Jun in the wheat - rice and wheat - maize - rice rotations. In the berseem - rice rotation, short-duration Palman 579 was planted in 1980-82 and PR103 was planted in 1983. Rice was transplanted about 20 Jun to be harvested in late Sep to allow timely sowing of berseem.

Rice did not respond significantly to direct P application in the three rotations (see table), indicating that P need not be applied to rice if the preceding rabi crop (wheat or berseem) has received recommended P fertilization. □

Effect of P application on rice yield in different crop rotations at PAU, Ludhiana, India.

P level (kg/ha)	Rice grain yield (t/ha)				
	1980	1981	1982	1983	Mean
<i>Wheat - rice</i>					
0	7.2	6.6	6.5	6.4	6.7
13	6.9	6.2	6.8	6.4	6.6
26	7.3	6.5	6.6	6.3	6.7
CD	ns	ns	ns	ns	
<i>Wheat - maize - rice</i>					
0	7.1	6.3	6.2	6.0	6.4
13	7.3	7.0	6.2	6.4	6.7
26	7.3	6.2	6.3	6.4	6.6
CD	ns	ns	ns	ns	
<i>Berseem - rice</i>					
0	5.8	5.5	5.3	7.4	6.0
13	5.3	5.7	5.3	7.4	5.9
26	5.4	5.9	5.7	7.2	6.0
CD	ns	ns	ns	ns	

Farmyard manure (FYM) in a rice - wheat rotation

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Organic manures can play an important role in soil productivity and crop yield. We sought to quantify N economy when FYM is applied to rice, and to ascertain the residual effect of the application on the succeeding wheat crop.

The 1979-83 experiment at the PAU Farm used a nonsaline loamy sand with pH 8.5, EC 0.25 mmho/cm, 0.24% organic carbon, and 90-70-146 kg available NPK/ha.

The FYM contained 0.63-0.30-0.90% NPK, and was applied at 12 t/ha, which added 76-36-108 kg NPK/ha to the soil.

Our data show that grain yield with 80 kg N and 12 t FYM/ha was comparable to that with 120 kg N/ha (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of FYM application on rice yield, Ludhiana, India.

Treatment		Grain yield (t/ha)					
N (kg/ha)	FYM (t/ha)	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	Mean
0	0	3.4	3.5	2.0	2.6	2.7	2.9
0	12	4.2	4.7	2.8	3.4	3.6	3.7
40	12	5.1	5.5	3.8	4.3	4.6	4.7
80	12	6.4	6.6	4.5	5.8	5.6	5.8
120	0	6.1	6.5	4.2	5.6	5.5	5.6

Rice - wheat is a common rotation in Punjab. A basal dose of 90-13-25 kg NPK/ha was applied to all wheat treatments except the control, and a standard 120-26-25 kg NPK/ha treatment.

Applying 90-13 kg NP/ha to wheat increased yield over the control (Table 2). Grain yield was 0.9 t/ha more if FYM was applied to the previous rice crop. This yield was comparable to that obtained with the recommended 120-26 kg NP/ha. The results indicate that applying 12 t FYM/ha to rice gave a residual effect

Table 2. Residual effect of FYM applied to rice on a succeeding wheat crop, Ludhiana, India.

Site no.	Treatment		Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
	N (kg/ha)	P (kg/ha)	
1	0	0	1.4
2	90	13	3.4
3	90	13	4.3 ^b
4	120	26	4.2

^a Av of 4 yr. ^b 12 t FYM/ha was applied to the previous rice crop.

equivalent to that from 30 kg N and 13 kg P/ha for the succeeding wheat crop. □